

Entrepreneurship in Coconut Cultivation: Comparing Behavioral Dimensions of Small and Big Farmers

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ABSTRACT

An entrepreneur is an innovator who connects new ideas or innovations with market opportunities in order to generate profit. Dimensions of entrepreneurial behavior encompass various traits and actions that define an entrepreneur's approach to business and innovation. An *Ex-post-facto* research design was used in the present study, Tumakuru and Hassan districts of Karnataka were purposively selected for the study. Three taluks from each district and three villages from each taluk were selected, followed by random selection of 180 coconut growers, including equal numbers of small and big farmers (five each per village) using simple random sampling. The results related to the entrepreneurial behaviour of coconut growers revealed that, more than two-fifth (43.33 %) of the respondents belongs to low level and medium level category among small and big coconut growers respectively and more than two-fifth (40.55 %) of the overall coconut

growers belongs to medium entrepreneurial behaviour category. Chi-square test indicates highly significant association at one per cent level between small and big coconut growers ($\chi^2 = 14.84$). the comparative analysis of entrepreneurial behaviour dimensions among coconut growers revealed that, dimensions such as risk orientation, decision-making ability and entrepreneurial skill showed significant differences at the 1 per cent level between small and large growers, while innovativeness, management orientation, leadership ability and market perception were significant at the 5 per cent level.

1. INTRODUCTION

The word “Entrepreneur” is derived from the French verb ‘entrepredre’, it means ‘to undertake’. An entrepreneur is an innovator who invariably links up the innovation with the market to earn a profit. The entrepreneur may adopt an innovation developed by others, re-invent or modify it, or develop an innovation not known earlier, to suit his / her particular purpose (Anil *et al.* 2025 a). There are numerous definitions of entrepreneurship, each developed within different contexts and schools of thought. It is widely recognized by analysts and economic theorists that entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship are key drivers of growth, job creation, innovation and productivity. Farming itself is an example of entrepreneurship involving, land, labour, inputs, capital, technology and risk marketing *etc.*, farmers use inputs, capital and labour to produce the end product. Entrepreneurial behavior is defined as identifying possibilities and putting good ideas into action. (Anil *et al.* 2025 a). Dimensions of entrepreneurial behavior encompass various traits and actions that define an entrepreneur's approach to business and innovation. (Anil *et al.* 2025 b). In the context of coconut farming, entrepreneurial behavior is essential for turning traditional practices into profitable, sustainable ventures.

Coconut, popularly known as *Kalpavriksha* or the “tree of heaven,” is a highly versatile crop in which almost every part of the plant has economic value, supporting the livelihood of nearly 15 million people in India. Cultivated in about 93 countries worldwide, coconut production is largely dominated by the Asia-Pacific region, with India emerging as one of the leading producers, mainly concentrated in southern states such as Kerala, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and Andhra Pradesh. The crop offers wide scope for value addition through kernel-based, water-based, inflorescence-based, shell-based and convenience food products, including coconut oil, milk, sugar, tender coconut water and coir-based industrial

materials. Coconut oil and virgin coconut oil have high nutritional and commercial importance, while by-products such as coir fiber, shell and wood contribute to multiple industries.

2. Review of Literature

Satish *et al.* (2017) concluded that, nearly half (49.17 %) of dairy farmers had medium level of source of information whereas, (31.67 %) had low, followed by 19.16 per cent dairy farmers with higher level of information seeking behavior. The plausible reasons for majority of dairy farmers under medium category of information seeking behaviour might be due to the fact that their middle level of education, medium interest and low exposure of improved dairy technologies.

Indumathi and Premavathi (2019) investigated that, more than two-third (67.70 %) of the respondents belonged to a medium entrepreneurial behaviour category. Exactly equal number of respondents belonged to low and high entrepreneurial behaviour category with 16.20 per cent. The plausible reason for most of the respondents with medium level of entrepreneurial behaviour might be the respondents have got good education, better income, moderately exposed to the mass media and society

Bushetti and Krishnamurthy (2022) identified the overall entrepreneurial behaviour score based on the cumulative raw scores of all the six dimensions which reveals that, more than two-third of (68.33 %) of the Byadagi chilli growers had medium level of entrepreneurial behaviour, followed by 19.45 per cent under low category and remaining (12.22 %) had high entrepreneurial behaviour.

Parganiha *et al.* (2023) revealed that, more than two-fifth (44.45 %) of the agripreneurs were having high level of management orientation whereas, 42.44 per cent of the members had medium level of management orientation and majority of the agripreneurs had high level of risk bearing ability (46.67 %), achievement motivation (42.22 %) and self-confidence (46.67 %), whereas, nearly half of the agripreneurs had medium level of knowledge of enterprise (48.89 %), leadership ability (46.67 %) and innovativeness (37.78 %).

Objective of the study:

To compare the entrepreneurial behavioural dimensions of small and big coconut farmers

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design

The study adopted an ex-post facto research design, which is an empirical method used to examine events or conditions that have already occurred and continue to exist. In this approach, the researcher does not manipulate the independent variables since they are naturally occurring or beyond experimental control. Therefore, conclusions regarding relationships among variables were drawn based on observed variations between independent and dependent factors without any direct intervention. This design is suitable for understanding behavioural patterns, exploring existing relationships and analyzing the circumstances under which such phenomena take place.

3.2 Selection of Respondents

Table 1: Sampling procedure used for selection of respondents

District	Taluks	Villages	Sample size (n = 180)	
			Small farmers (n ₁ = 90)	Big farmers (n ₂ = 90)
Tumakuru	Gubbi	K. Rampura	5	5
		Kadaba	5	5
		D. Rampura	5	5
	Turuvekere	Devihalli	5	5
		Haralikere	5	5
		Kardigere	5	5
	Tiptur	Ramanahalli	5	5
		Chikkabidire	5	5
		Mattihalli	5	5
Hassan	Arsikere	N. Gollarahatti	5	5
		Motihalli	5	5
		Halebeedu	5	5
	Channarayapatna	Gowdgera	5	5
		Hombale Koplpu	5	5
		Ragibommanahalli	5	5
	Arkalgud	Kabaligere	5	5
		Attimarkoplpu	5	5
		Ramanathapura	5	5

Total	6 taluks	18 villages	90	90
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Tumakuru and Hassan districts of Karnataka were purposively selected for the study due to their prominence in coconut cultivation, ranking first and second respectively in terms of area and production, and playing a significant role in the state’s coconut economy and market activities. From Tumakuru district, the taluks of Gubbi, Turuvekere and Tiptur, and from Hassan district, Arsikere, Channarayapatna and Arkalgud were selected based on higher coconut cultivation area and production. From each selected taluk, three villages were randomly chosen, resulting in a total of 18 villages for the study. A sample of 180 coconut growers was selected using simple random sampling, ensuring equal representation of small and big farmers, with five small and five big coconut growers selected from each village for data collection through personal interviews.

3.3 Measurement of Entrepreneurial Behaviour

A standardized scale to measure entrepreneurial behaviour among coconut growers was developed and the final scale consists of 43 statements. The respondents were asked to indicate the degree of their agreement to these statements on five-point continuum of “Strongly agree”, “Agree”, “Undecided”, “Disagree” and “Strongly disagree” with a weightage of 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The scoring pattern was reversed for negative statements. The sum of the scores obtained by the respondent was taken as his or her score of Entrepreneurial behaviour of coconut growers. The possible score ranged from 43 to 215.

Based on the total cumulated score obtained, the coconut growers were classified in to three categories *viz.*, high, medium and low entrepreneurial behaviour level based on the mean and standard deviation as a measure of check. (Likert, 1932).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of the responses from small and big coconut growers of Tumakuru and Hassan districts across various dimensions are indicated below. The results in the Table 2 revealed variations in entrepreneurial behavioural dimensions among coconut growers. Under innovativeness, farmers were mostly cautious while trying new practices (MS = 3.46), followed by early adoption of new technologies (MS = 3.42), while adoption of mechanization recorded the lowest score (MS = 2.47). Achievement motivation was high, with farmers strongly focusing on achieving optimal yield and quality (MS = 4.23). Decision-making ability showed high self-reliance, as farmers preferred deciding suitable technologies

independently (MS = 4.54). In risk orientation, respondents agreed that taking risk is necessary for success (MS = 3.92), though willingness to take uncertain risks was relatively lower (MS = 2.81). Management orientation emphasized farm planning (MS = 3.70), while leadership ability was reflected through active participation in discussions and trainings (MS = 4.08). Economic motivation was strong, particularly in adopting practices that ensure higher profits (MS = 4.52). Scientific orientation indicated positive perception towards scientific application (MS = 3.32), whereas market perception showed preference for direct marketing and reliance on market information. Entrepreneurial orientation highlighted recognition of consumer preferences (MS = 3.52), and entrepreneurial skills were higher in value-addition abilities (MS = 3.72) compared to formal training exposure such as FoCT programmes (MS = 2.76).

Table 2: Statement wise distribution of coconut growers with respect to entrepreneurial behaviour

Sl. No.	Statements	Small (n1=90)		Big (n2=90)		Overall (n=180)	
		Mean score	Rank	Mean score	Rank	Mean score	Rank
A	Innovativeness						
1	I prefer to adopt any new technology in coconut production before others in the society	3.32	I	3.52	II	3.42	II
2	I am cautious about trying a new practice in coconut production	3.16	II	3.77	I	3.46	I
3	I like to keep up to date information about new farming practices of coconut production	2.97	III	3.19	IV	3.08	III
4	I prefer adhering to traditional approaches in coconut production rather than embracing newer methods	2.60	IV	3.28	III	2.94	IV
5	I try to adopt mechanization in coconut cultivation that enhances efficiency and reduce labour costs	2.58	V	2.37	V	2.47	V
B	Achievement motivation						

1	I always prefer to be actively focused in coconut cultivation for achieving optimal yields and quality in the coconut farming industry rather than taking rest	4.20	I	4.27	I	4.23	I
2	I always strive to be the best coconut producer/entrepreneur	3.80	II	3.78	II	3.79	II
3	I would like to give up at something that prove to be excessively challenging or unattainable	3.59	IV	3.56	V	3.57	IV
4	Current circumstances are discouraging me to work hard for achieving potentiality in coconut production	3.47	V	3.59	IV	3.53	V
5	Awards, government policies and recognition motivates me to get better yield in coconut farming	3.83	III	3.60	III	3.72	III
C	Decision making ability						
1	I myself decide the suitable technologies for coconut cultivation in my farm land for getting higher returns	4.47	I	4.62	I	4.54	I
2	I collect information from various sources about innovative methods and carefully evaluate the pros and cons before making decision	3.66	II	4.17	II	3.91	II
3	I abide by the decisions taken by my fellow farmers / family members / parents / development department / research stations / KVKs	3.40	III	3.84	III	3.62	III
D	Risk orientation						
1	I financially invest in advanced coconut cultivation technologies, that can bring me advantages in the future	3.19	II	3.90	II	3.54	II
2	It is necessary to take some risk, if a farmer	3.77	I	4.08	I	3.92	I

	wants to become successful						
3	I am ready to take risk in coconut cultivation even though the rate of success is unknown	2.32	III	3.30	III	2.81	III
E	Management orientation						
1	Increasing the yield in coconut cultivation will be easier with the implementation of a farm production plan	3.59	I	3.81	I	3.70	I
2	Hiring skilled labour who undergone FoCT (Friends of Coconut Tree) programme is beneficial for me during coconut harvesting	2.97	IV	3.81	I	3.07	IV
3	I plant and get income from other farm enterprises such as cultivating crops like banana and pulse crops during the juvenile phase of coconut cultivation	3.49	II	3.69	III	3.59	II
4	Consulting a horticulture expert is essential for effective coconut cultivation	3.20	III	3.52	IV	3.36	III
F	Leadership ability						
1	I always try to participate and take lead in discussion on new technologies of coconut cultivation in group meetings, trainings, demonstrations etc.	3.90	I	4.26	I	4.08	I
2	I assign the work to my labour and family members by recognizing their diverse skills in coconut cultivation and its value addition	3.32	II	3.52	III	3.42	III
3	I share the ideas of new technologies to my village people who consult me for the information regarding coconut cultivation	3.19	III	3.84	II	3.52	II
G	Economic motivation						
1	I work towards maximizing yield and net profit with minimal / optimal inputs	4.46	I	4.43	II	4.44	II
2	I take up value addition in coconut to	4.27	III	4.16	III	4.21	III

	maximize monetary profits, instead of focusing solely on selling of coconut nuts						
3	I will consider adopting new methods of coconut cultivation and processing only when I am convinced that they result in higher profit/returns	4.42	II	4.61	I	4.52	I
4	It is essential to me, to earn a living out of coconut farming but the most significant aspects of life cannot be solely defined in economic terms	4.20	IV	4.04	IV	4.12	IV
H	Scientific orientation						
1	I believe that application of science in coconut cultivation means saving of financial and natural resources	3.32	I	3.31	II	3.32	I
2	I believe that staying informed about emerging scientific technologies is not beneficial in the context of coconut cultivation	2.80	III	3.03	III	2.92	III
3	Having good rapport with scientists and officers helps me to acquire scientific knowledge on coconut cultivation	3.11	II	3.43	I	3.27	II
I	Market perception						
1	I believe that market news is not so useful to a coconut farmer	3.63	I	3.71	I	3.67	I
2	I can secure a favorable price for my coconut products in the market by incorporating value addition	3.30	IV	3.37	IV	3.33	IV
3	I always sell my coconut products to the nearest market irrespective of price	2.66	VI	3.29	VI	2.97	VI
4	I always purchase the inputs for coconut farming from the shop where my neighbors/relatives purchase	3.61	III	3.59	II	3.6	III

5	I sell the coconut produce directly in the market without involving middle man to get better price	3.62	II	3.59	II	3.61	II
6	I always keep track of what my competitors are doing in the market and accordingly I decide my marketing strategy for selling coconut products	3.14	V	3.34	V	3.24	V
J	Entrepreneurial orientation						
1	I possess all the capabilities required to become a successful entrepreneur in coconut farming	3.08	IV	3.31	II	3.19	III
2	I always try to read/listen literature/programmes related to coconut cultivation, processing and value addition	3.17	II	3.30	III	3.23	II
4	I never estimate the financial requirements for coconut production, value addition and marketing	3.09	III	3.07	IV	3.08	IV
5	I always recognize the consumer preference for coconut-based products in a market and try to produce, add value and sell that type of products accordingly	3.38	I	3.66	I	3.52	I
K	Entrepreneurial skill						
1	I possess the skills to prepare value added products in coconut	3.54	I	3.89	II	3.72	I
2	It is enough to know cultivation practices of coconut, rather than knowing processing, value addition and marketing aspects	3.38	II	3.90	I	3.64	II
3	I always undergone FoCT (Friends of Coconut Tree) programme which help me during harvesting and plant protection activities.	2.34	III	3.18	III	2.76	III

The findings suggest that coconut growers exhibit moderate to high entrepreneurial behaviour characterized by cautious innovation, strong achievement motivation and independent decision-making. Farmers appear willing to adopt new technologies after careful evaluation, indicating risk-aware behaviour shaped by economic uncertainties in agriculture. High economic motivation and emphasis on profit-oriented decisions reflect commercialization trends in coconut cultivation. Limited mechanization adoption and lower participation in skill-based programmes may be due to labour availability, investment constraints or limited technical exposure. Active leadership participation and positive scientific orientation indicate openness to learning and extension support, while market-related responses show increasing awareness of value addition and direct marketing for better returns. Overall, the results imply that coconut farmers are gradually transitioning toward an entrepreneurial and market-oriented production system while balancing innovation with risk management.

Table 3: Overall Entrepreneurial behaviour of coconut growers

Sl. No.	Entrepreneurial behaviour		Small (n ₁ =90)		Big (n ₂ =90)		Overall (n=180)	
			f	%	f	%	f	%
1	Coconut growers Mean: 151.67 SD: 12.22	Low < (145.56)	39	43.33	9	10.00	48	26.67
		Medium (145.56 – 157.78)	34	37.78	39	43.33	73	40.55
		High > (150.22)	17	18.89	42	46.67	59	32.78
Chi square value			14.84**					

The Table 3, depicted the entrepreneurial behavior of coconut growers, the overall mean score was 151.67, with more than two fifth (43.33 %) of the respondents belongs to low level and medium level category among small and big coconut growers respectively and more than two-fifth (40.55 %) of the overall coconut growers belongs to medium entrepreneurial behaviour category Chi-square test indicates highly significant association at one per cent level between small and big coconut growers towards entrepreneurial behaviour ($\chi^2 = 14.84$). The findings are in the line with (Indumathi and Premavathi, 2019).

When comparing small and big coconut growers, it is evident that big farmers tend to show higher levels of entrepreneurial behaviour, likely due to their farms size, better access to resources and stronger

market presence. Small farmers, though showing potential, may benefit from targeted support in market access, technical guidance and financial assistance to improve their entrepreneurial outcomes.

Table 4: Dimension wise distribution of entrepreneurial behaviour among coconut growers in Karnataka

Sl. No.	Entrepreneurial behaviour dimensions	Categories	Small (n ₁ =90)	Big (n ₂ =90)	Overall (n=180)
			f (%)	f (%)	f (%)
1.	Innovativeness Mean = 15.37 SD = 3.08	Low < (13.83)	35 (38.89)	21 (23.33)	56 (31.11)
		Medium (13.83 – 16.91)	20 (22.22)	20 (22.22)	40 (22.22)
		High > (16.91)	35 (38.89)	49 (54.44)	84 (46.67)
2.	Achievement motivation Mean = 18.84 SD = 2.31	Low < (17.68)	24 (26.67)	19 (21.11)	43 (23.89)
		Medium (17.68 – 19.99)	34 (37.78)	35 (38.89)	69 (38.33)
		High > (19.99)	32 (35.56)	36 (40.00)	68 (37.78)
3.	Decision making ability Mean = 12.08 SD = 2.16	Low < (11.00)	29 (32.22)	12 (13.33)	41 (22.78)
		Medium (11.00 – 13.16)	46 (51.11)	39 (43.33)	85 (47.22)
		High > (13.16)	15 (16.67)	39 (43.34)	54 (30.00)
4.	Risk orientation Mean = 10.28 SD = 2.22	Low < (9.16)	44 (48.89)	11 (12.22)	55 (30.56)
		Medium (9.16 – 11.39)	40 (44.44)	36 (40.00)	76 (42.22)
		High > (11.39)	6	43	49

			(6.67)	(47.78)	(27.22)
5.	Management orientation Mean = 13.72 SD = 3.04	Low < (12.19)	32 (35.56)	26 (28.89)	58 (32.22)
		Medium (12.19 – 15.24)	35 (38.88)	27 (30.00)	62 (34.44)
		High > (15.24)	23 (25.56)	37 (41.11)	60 (33.34)
6.	Leadership ability Mean = 11.02 SD = 1.94	Low < (10.04)	38 (42.22)	20 (22.22)	58 (32.22)
		Medium (10.04 – 11.99)	19 (21.11)	19 (21.11)	38 (21.11)
		High > (11.99)	33 (36.67)	51 (56.67)	84 (46.67)
7.	Economic motivation Mean = 17.29 SD = 1.50	Low < (16.54)	25 (27.78)	25 (27.78)	50 (27.78)
		Medium (16.54 – 18.04)	44 (48.89)	46 (51.11)	90 (50.00)
		High > (18.04)	21 (23.33)	19 (21.11)	40 (22.22)
8.	Scientific orientation Mean = 9.51 SD = 2.21	Low < (8.39)	33 (36.67)	23 (25.56)	56 (31.11)
		Medium (8.39 – 10.61)	29 (32.22)	28 (31.11)	57 (31.67)
		High > (10.61)	28 (31.11)	39 (43.33)	67 (37.220)
9.	Market perception Mean = 20.43 SD = 2.77	Low < (19.03)	38 (42.22)	26 (28.89)	64 (35.56)
		Medium (19.03 – 21.81)	35 (38.89)	24 (26.67)	59 (32.78)
		High > (21.81)	17 (18.89)	40 (44.44)	57 (31.67)
10.	Entrepreneurial	Low < (11.50)	29	29	58

	orientation Mean = 13.02 SD = 3.04		(32.22)	(32.22)	(32.22)
		Medium (11.50 – 14.54)	27 (30.00)	18 (20.00)	45 (25.00)
		High > (14.54)	34 (37.78)	43 (47.78)	77 (42.78)
11.	Entrepreneurial skill Mean = 10.12 SD = 1.86	Low < (9.18)	43 (47.78)	12 (13.33)	55 (30.56)
		Medium (9.18 – 11.04)	41 (45.56)	46 (51.11)	87 (48.33)
		High > (11.04)	6 (6.66)	32 (35.56)	38 (21.11)

The findings in Table 4, revealed the overall analysis of entrepreneurial behaviour across dimensions in the two districts. Regarding innovativeness, more than two-fifths (46.67 %) of coconut growers exhibit high innovativeness, followed by slightly less than one-third (31.11 %) belong to the low category however, 22.22 per cent belong to the medium category, (Mean = 13.92). For achievement motivation, nearly two-fifths (38.33 %) of coconut growers belong to the medium category, followed by a slight less than that proportion (37.78 %) exhibit high motivation, while 23.89 per cent belong to the low category, (Mean = 18.84).

In decision-making ability, nearly half (47.22 %) of coconut growers belong to the medium category, followed by 30.00 per cent exhibit high decision-making ability, while 22.78 per cent belong to the low category, (Mean = 12.08). Regarding Risk Orientation, more than two-fifths (42.22 %) of coconut growers belong to the medium category followed by a smaller proportion (27.22 %) exhibit high risk orientation, while 30.56 per cent comes under low category, (Mean = 10.28). In Management Orientation, more than one-third (34.44 %) belong to the medium category, followed by one-third (33.34 %) of coconut growers demonstrate high management orientation, while 32.22 per cent belong to the low category, (Mean = 13.72). For Leadership Ability, nearly half (46.67 %) of coconut growers demonstrate high leadership ability, while a slight less than one-third (32.22 %) belong to the low category, (Mean = 11.02).

Regarding economic motivation, half (50.00 %) of the respondents belong to the medium category, followed by smaller proportions exhibit low (27.78 %) and high (22.22 %) economic motivation, (Mean = 17.29). In scientific orientation, less than two-fifths (37.22 %) exhibit high scientific

orientation, while 31.11 per cent belong to the low category (Mean = 9.51). Regarding market perception, more than one-third (35.56 %) belong to the low category, followed by smaller proportions (31.67 %) exhibit high market perception (Mean = 20.43). In entrepreneurial orientation, more than two-fifths (42.78 %) exhibit high entrepreneurial orientation, followed by a quarter (25.00 %) belong to the medium category and 32.22 per cent to the low category, (Mean = 13.02). For entrepreneurial skill, nearly half (48.33 %) of coconut growers belong to the medium category, followed by smaller proportions (30.56 %) exhibit low skills, while 21.11 per cent demonstrate high entrepreneurial skills, (Mean = 10.12). The results are supported by (Archana ,2013)

Table 5: Comparative analysis of entrepreneurial behaviour dimensions among coconut growers

Sl. No.	Dimension	Small (n1=90)	Big (n2=90)	Mann-Whitney U Test
		Mean rank	Mean rank	Z Value
1	Innovativeness	78.28	102.72	3.172*
2	Achievement motivation	88.72	92.28	0.465 ^{NS}
3	Decision making ability	76.42	104.58	3.676**
4	Risk orientation	68.20	112.80	5.812**
5	Management orientation	82.02	98.98	2.204*
6	Leadership ability	82.35	101.21	2.531*
7	Economic motivation	92.24	88.76	0.457 ^{NS}
8	Scientific orientation	83.77	97.23	1.751 ^{NS}
9	Market perception	81.10	99.90	2.442*
10	Entrepreneurial orientation	85.16	91.84	1.389 ^{NS}
11	Entrepreneurial skill	67.56	113.44	6.012**
	Overall	69.23	111.77	5.480**

Note: ** and * denote significance at 1 per cent and 5 per cent levels, respectively and NS- Non significant

The Table 5, highlighted the comparative analysis of entrepreneurial behaviour dimensions among coconut growers, revealing significant differences between small and big growers in several areas, underscoring the impact of farm size on entrepreneurial traits. Dimensions such as risk orientation, decision-making ability and entrepreneurial skill show significant differences at the 1 per cent level

between small and big growers, the probable reason might be due to their ability to take calculated risks, make informed decisions and exhibit advanced entrepreneurial skills and exposure to innovative practices. Dimensions such as innovativeness, management orientation, leadership ability and market perception are significant at the 5 per cent level. The higher innovativeness and leadership ability observed among big growers might be due to their capacity to adopt new techniques, better market perception and greater network as expressed by farmers in the study area.

Dimensions such as achievement motivation, economic motivation, scientific orientation and entrepreneurial orientation show no significant differences. This suggests that these traits are not strongly influenced by farm size and may be equally distributed across both small and big growers. The reason might be that, the personal ambition, local conditions and external influences, such as extension services, may have a more significant impact on these dimensions.

Overall, big growers exhibit significantly higher entrepreneurial behavior compared to small growers, as indicated by the Mann-Whitney U Test results at the 1 per cent level. The results highlighted the pivotal role of farm size in shaping entrepreneurial traits. However, these findings underscore the importance of supporting small growers through targeted interventions, such as training programs, better access to resources and enhanced market integration, to improve their entrepreneurial capacity and reduce the gaps observed. The similar findings were found with (Bushetti and Krishnamurthy, 2023).

5. CONCLUSION

The study concluded that coconut growers in Tumakuru and Hassan districts exhibited moderate to high entrepreneurial behaviour, with farmers showing strong achievement motivation, economic orientation and independent decision-making ability. Growers adopted innovations cautiously, balancing opportunities with risk considerations, while leadership participation and value-addition skills reflected an increasing shift toward market-oriented coconut cultivation. However, lower mechanization adoption and limited participation in skill-based programmes indicated constraints related to investment capacity, technical exposure and access to trained labour.

Comparative analysis revealed that big farmers possessed significantly higher entrepreneurial behaviour, particularly in risk orientation, decision-making ability and entrepreneurial skills, mainly due to better resource availability and market exposure, whereas entrepreneurial aspirations such as achievement and economic motivation were similar across farm sizes. The findings suggest the need for policy support focusing on strengthening extension services, improving access to training, credit and

market linkages, and promoting value addition and mechanization to enhance entrepreneurial capacity, especially among small growers, thereby enabling inclusive and sustainable development of the coconut sector.

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